

Kinetics and Mechanism of uncatalysed and Chloride-catalysed Oxidative Decarboxylation of Glycine and Aspartic Acid by Chloramine-T in Perchloric Acid Medium

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The kinetics of oxidative decarboxylation of glycine and L-aspartic acid by chloramine-T has been investigated both in the absence and presence of chloride ion in perchloric acid medium. In the absence of chloride ion, the rate followed second order kinetics in [CAT]₀, first order in [substrate], inverse first order in [H⁺] with both the amino acids. Chloride was found to enhance the rate of oxidation and affect the kinetics. In the presence of chloride, the rate followed first order kinetics in [CAT]₀ in both cases. But the rate was fractional and zero order in [substrate] with glycine and aspartic acid, respectively. The kinetic order in [H⁺] was also different, *i.e.* inverse fractional order and fractional order respectively with glycine and aspartic acid. The effect of chloride was more pronounced with aspartic acid. Effects of added reaction product and the variation of ionic strength and dielectric constant of the reaction medium have also been investigated. Reaction schemes in conformity with the observed kinetics have been proposed and the related rate laws derived. The constants of the rate limiting and other steps have been calculated in some cases.

MECHANISM of oxidative decarboxylation of amino acids has attracted the attention of many workers¹⁻⁹. It is one of the important biochemical processes and is a potential area for intensive investigation. In an effort to arrive at a comprehensive reaction scheme to explain the course of the positive chlorine reactions under varying conditions of acidity and chloride concentrations, we report herein the kinetics of oxidative decarboxylation of glycine and L-aspartic acid by chloramine-T in perchloric acid medium both in the presence and absence of chloride ion.

Experimental

An aqueous solution of chloramine-T (Fluka, A.G.) was standardised by iodometric method. Chromatographically pure glycine (Gly) and L-aspartic acid (ASP) (Sisco, India) were used and their aqueous stock solutions were standardised by reported methods. All other reagents used were of AnalaR grade. The ionic strength of the medium was kept at a high value by adding concentrated solutions of sodium perchlorate.

Kinetic runs were carried out under pseudo-first or second order conditions using at least 5- to 10-fold excess of [amino acid] over [CAT]. A mixture containing known amounts of amino acid, HClO₄, NaClO₄, (to maintain ionic strength) and H₂O (to keep the volume constant for all runs) was thermally equilibrated at 313 K. The reaction was initiated by rapidly adding a measured amount of CAT solution, pre-equilibrated at the same temperature, to the mixture, and the progress of the reaction was monitored for two half-lives by iodometric

determination of unreacted CAT at regular intervals of time. The rate constants computed by the method of least-squares were reproducible within $\pm 3\%$.

Stoichiometry and product analysis: The stoichiometry of CAT-amino acid oxidations were determined both in the absence and presence of Cl⁻ in perchloric acid medium (0.02–0.10 mol dm⁻³), by equilibrating varying ratios of [CAT] to [amino acid] at 313 K for different intervals of time. Nitrile was the major product in the absence of Cl⁻, and aldehyde in the presence of Cl⁻. It was also noticed that aldehydes do not get oxidised under the present experimental conditions. The nitriles and aldehydes were identified by conventional tests^{10,11} and recording the spectra of the reaction mixtures. *p*-Toluene-sulphonamide (PTS), the reduced product of CAT, was detected by paper chromatography with benzyl alcohol saturated with water as the solvent and 0.5% vanillin (in 1% HCl solution in ether) as the spray reagent. The observed stoichiometries may be represented by equation (1) and (2).

where, R = CH₂C₆H₄SO₂, R' = H (glycine) and CH₂COOH (aspartic acid).

Results

Kinetics of oxidations of Gly and Asp by CAT in perchloric acid medium was studied at several initial

concentrations of the reactants, both in the absence and presence of chloride ion. The results are shown in Tables 1-4.

Kinetics in absence of Cl⁻ : At constant [HClO₄], with several fold excess of amino acid plots of 1/[CAT] vs time were linear upto 75% completion of reaction with both the amino acids and pseudo-second order rate constants were unaffected by the changes in initial concentrations of the oxidant. The rate increased with increase in [amino acid] at constant [HClO₄] and [CAT]. The log-log plots of *k*_{obs} vs [amino acid] were linear with unit slopes in both the cases establishing first order kinetics in [amino acid]. But the rates decreased

with increase in [acid] with both the amino acids. The log-log plots were linear with unit negative slopes showing inverse first order dependence on [H⁺].

Kinetics in presence of Cl⁻ : Chloride ion was found to catalyse the reaction. The rate followed first order kinetics in [CAT] as against second order kinetics observed in the absence of Cl⁻. The log [CAT]₀/[CAT] vs time plots were linear for two half-lives and pseudo-first order rate constants were unaffected by the changes in [CAT]₀ with both the amino acids. At constant [CAT], [amino acid] and [Cl⁻], the rate decreased with increase in [HClO₄] with glycine and increased with aspartic acid. The

TABLE 1—PSEUDO-FIRST/SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR OXIDATION OF GLYCINE (Gly) BY CHLORAMINE-T (CAT) AT 313 K

[Gly] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	[CAT] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	[HClO ₄] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	[Cl ⁻] × 10 mol dm ⁻³	In absence of Cl ⁻ <i>k</i> _{obs} × 10 dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	In presence of Cl ⁻ <i>k</i> _{obs} × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹
1.0	2.0	5.0	1.0	1.97	3.5
2.0	2.0	5.0	1.0	2.91	5.8
5.0	2.0	5.0	1.0	6.95	10.9
10.0	2.0	5.0	1.0	13.50	19.5
2.0	2.0	0.5	1.0	25.50	—
2.0	2.0	1.0	1.0	12.20	—
2.0	2.0	1.5	1.0	—	13.3
2.0	2.0	2.0	1.0	7.30	—
2.0	2.0	3.0	1.0	—	8.7
2.0	2.0	5.0	1.0	2.91	5.8
2.0	2.0	10.0	1.0	1.35	4.1
2.0	2.0	20.0	1.0	—	2.9
2.0	0.5	5.0	1.0	2.95	5.8
2.0	1.0	5.0	1.0	2.86	5.9
2.0	2.0	5.0	1.0	2.91	5.8
2.0	4.0	5.0	1.0	2.96	5.8
2.0	2.0	5.0	0.2	—	4.0
2.0	2.0	5.0	0.5	—	4.8
2.0	2.0	5.0	1.0	—	5.8
2.0	2.0	5.0	2.0	—	6.6

TABLE 2—PSEUDO-FIRST AND SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR OXIDATION OF ASPARTIC ACID (Asp) BY CHLORAMINE-T (CAT) AT 313 K

[Asp] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	[CAT] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	[HClO ₄] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	[Cl ⁻] × 10 mol dm ⁻³	In absence of Cl ⁻ <i>k</i> _{obs} × 10 dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	In presence of Cl ⁻ <i>k</i> _{obs} × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹
0.5	1.0	5.0	1.0	0.67	18.6
1.0	1.0	5.0	1.0	1.26	19.0
2.0	1.0	5.0	1.0	2.52	19.2
5.0	1.0	5.0	1.0	5.80	18.9
1.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	22.40	—
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	11.40	—
1.0	1.0	2.0	1.0	5.16	10.5
1.0	1.0	5.0	1.0	1.26	19.0
1.0	1.0	10.0	1.0	0.94	33.4
1.0	1.0	20.0	1.0	—	50.1
1.0	0.2	5.0	1.0	1.28	19.8
1.0	0.5	5.0	1.0	1.21	18.9
1.0	1.0	5.0	1.0	1.26	19.0
1.0	2.0	5.0	1.0	1.26	19.5
1.0	1.0	5.0	0.2	—	5.7
1.0	1.0	5.0	0.5	—	10.8
1.0	1.0	5.0	1.0	—	19.0
1.0	1.0	5.0	2.0	—	36.6

TABLE 3—EFFECTS OF VARIATIONS IN SOLVENT COMPOSITION, IONIC STRENGTH AND PRODUCT (PTS) ON RATE OF OXIDATION OF Gly AND Asp BY CAT AT 313 K

Methanol %	In the absence of Cl ⁻		In the presence of Cl ⁻ (0.1 mol dm ⁻³)	
	<i>k</i> _{obs} (× 10 ³ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)		<i>k</i> _{obs} × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	
	Gly ^a	Asp ^b	Gly ^a	Asp ^b
0	2.91	1.25	5.8	19.0
10	1.88	1.07	5.6	18.9
20	1.19	0.78	4.9	18.5
30	0.88	0.58	4.2	18.6
40	0.51	0.45	3.8	18.9
μ				
0.2	2.89	1.25	5.8	18.9
0.4	2.91	1.26	5.8	19.1
0.5	2.92	1.25	5.8	19.0
0.75	2.90	1.25	5.8	19.0
[PTS]				
0.001	2.91	1.26	5.8	19.0
0.002	2.92	1.25	5.8	19.1
0.005	2.90	1.25	5.8	19.0

^a10³[CAT]=10³[Gly]=40[HClO₄]=2.0 mol dm⁻³. ^b10³[CAT]=10³[Asp]=20[HClO₄]=1.0 mol dm⁻³.

log - log plots of *k*_{obs} vs [H⁺] were linear with fractional slopes of -0.62 and 0.73 with glycine and aspartic acid, respectively, establishing inverse fractional and fractional kinetics in [H⁺] in two cases. The rate increased with increase in [Gly] with a fractional order dependence and was independent of [Asp]. The rates increased with increase in [Cl⁻] with both the amino acids with fractional order dependence on [Cl⁻] (Table 4).

TABLE 4—KINETIC DATA AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR OXIDATION OF GLYCINE AND ASPARTIC ACID BY CHLORAMINE-T

Order observed in	In the absence of Cl ⁻		In the presence Cl ⁻ (0.1 mol dm ⁻³)	
	Gly	Asp	Gly	Asp
[Amino acid]	1.0	1.0	0.59	0
[H ⁺]	-1.0	-1.0	-0.62	0.73
[CAT]	2.0	2.0	1.0	1.0
[Cl ⁻]	—	—	0.22	0.81
<i>E</i> _a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	69.9	58.9	84.2	64.4
log <i>A</i>	7.3	5.4	10.8	8.0
Δ <i>H</i> [‡] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	66.7	56.3	81.6	61.7
Δ <i>S</i> [‡] (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-105.2	-141.7	-98.9	-92.1
Δ <i>G</i> [‡] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	99.6	100.7	93.6	90.6

Addition of the reaction product PTS and the variation of ionic strength of the medium had no significant effect on the rate both in the absence and presence of Cl⁻. The activation parameters were computed by studying the rates at different temperatures.

Discussion

The dissociation of amino acids is pH dependent^{1,2}.

Chloramine T (RNCINa, where R=CH₃C₆H₄-SO₂) is a strong electrolyte in aqueous solution, and depending upon pH of the medium it furnishes different types of oxidising species^{1,3-15}.

The following equilibria exist in its aqueous solutions,

The probable reactive species in the acid solutions are RNHCl, RNCl₂, HOCl and possibly H₂OCl⁺ in the absence of Cl⁻, and Cl₂ in the presence of Cl⁻ at high hydrogen ion concentrations^{1,6,17}.

Mechanism of oxidation: The following common mechanistic schemes have been proposed to account for the observed kinetics for the oxidation of Gly and Asp by CAT in acid medium both in the absence and presence of Cl⁻.

In the absence of Cl⁻: The kinetics of second order in [CAT], first order in [substrate] and inverse first order in [H⁺] can be explained through Scheme 1 which involves (i) rapid deprotonation of amino acid cation, (ii) rapid formation of chloro intermediate by the interaction of the oxidising species RNHCl and the carboxylate group of the amino acid, (iii) slow abstraction of hydride ion from the intermediate in the rate limiting step and

(iv) rapid decomposition of the intermediate to the products as shown in Scheme 2.

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

The related rate law is

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{-d[\text{CAT}]}{dt} &= \frac{K_2 k_3 [\text{CAT}]^2 [\text{S}]}{[\text{H}_2\text{O}]} = \frac{K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{CAT}]^2 [\text{SH}^+]}{[\text{H}^+] [\text{H}_2\text{O}]} \\
 \text{or} \\
 k_{\text{obs}} &= \frac{K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{SH}^+]}{[\text{H}^+] [\text{H}_2\text{O}]} = \frac{K_2 k_3 [\text{S}]}{[\text{H}_2\text{O}]} \quad (11)
 \end{aligned}$$

The plots of k_{obs} vs $1/[\text{H}^+]$ and k_{obs} vs $[\text{S}]$ were linear (Fig. 1) in accordance with rate law (11).

In the presence of Cl^- : Chloride was found to enhance the rate with both glycine and aspartic acid. But the effect was more pronounced with the latter.

(i) The kinetics of first order in $[\text{CAT}]$, fractional order each in $[\text{S}]$ and $[\text{Cl}^-]$ and inverse fractional order in $[\text{H}^+]$ can be explained through Scheme 3.

Scheme 3

Fig. 1. (a) Plot of k_{obs} vs $1/[\text{H}^+]$: (●) Gly and (×) Asp, $[\text{Gly}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{CAT}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{Asp}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{CAT}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. (b) Plot of k_{obs} vs $[\text{Amino acid}]$: (●) Gly and (×) Asp, $[\text{HClO}_4] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{CAT}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (Gly), $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (Asp).

The rate law (12) has been obtained by applying steady state approximation to the intermediates Y

and Y',

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAT}]}{dt} = \frac{K_5 K_7 k_6 k'_8 [\text{CAT}][\text{S}][\text{Cl}^-][\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{1 + K_5[\text{Cl}^-] + K_7[\text{S}] + K_5 K_7[\text{S}][\text{Cl}^-]} \quad (12)$$

or

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{K_5 K_7 k_6 k'_8 [\text{S}][\text{Cl}^-]}{1 + K_5[\text{Cl}^-] + K_7[\text{S}] + K_5 K_7[\text{S}][\text{Cl}^-]} \quad (13)$$

or

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{K_1 K_2 K_7 k_6 k'_8 [\text{SH}^+][\text{Cl}^-]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_5[\text{Cl}^-][\text{H}^+] + K_1 K_7 [\text{SH}^+] + K_1 K_5 K_7 [\text{SH}^+][\text{Cl}^-]}$$

or

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \left\{ \frac{1}{K_7 k_6 k'_8} + \frac{1}{K_5 K_7 k_6 k'_8 [\text{Cl}^-]} \right\} \frac{1}{[\text{S}]} + \frac{1}{K_5 k_6 k'_8 [\text{Cl}^-]} + \frac{1}{k_6 k'_8} \quad (14)$$

The plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{S}]$ was linear with an intercept on ordinate (Fig. 2) in conformity with rate law (14). From the slope and intercept, the

Fig. 2. (a) Plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{Gly}]$, $[\text{CAT}] = 2.0 \times 10^3$ mol dm^{-3} , $[\text{HOClO}_4] = 5.0 \times 10^3$ mol dm^{-3} , $[\text{Cl}^-] = 0.1$ mol dm^{-3} . (b) Plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{Cl}^-]$, $[\text{Gly}] = 2.0 \times 10^3$ mol dm^{-3} , $[\text{CAT}] = 2.0 \times 10^3$ mol dm^{-3} , $[\text{HOClO}_4] = 5.0 \times 10^3$ mol dm^{-3} .

equilibrium constant K_7 (=intercept/slope) was calculated (16.75 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$).

The rate law (13) can also be written as

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \left\{ \frac{1}{K_5 k_6 k'_8} + \frac{1}{K_5 K_7 k_6 k'_8 [\text{S}]} \right\} \frac{1}{[\text{Cl}^-]} + \frac{1}{K_7 k_6 k'_8 [\text{S}]} + \frac{1}{k_6 k'_8} \quad (15)$$

The plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{Cl}^-]$ was also linear with $K_5 = 69.2 \text{ dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ (Fig. 2).

Scheme 3 depicts the decomposition of CAT in presence of Cl^- , to HOCl which in turn interacts

with glycine in a slow step to give products. This has been verified independently by studying the kinetics of oxidation of glycine by HOCl (Table 5). Identical kinetics observed with HOCl provides an additional support to the proposed reaction mechanism.

TABLE 5—PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR OXIDATION OF GLYCINE BY HOCl AT 308 K

[Gly] $\times 10^3$ mol dm^{-3}	[HOClO ₄] $\times 10^3$ mol dm^{-3}	[CAT] $\times 10^3$ mol dm^{-3}	$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$
1.0	5.0	2.0	3.34
1.5	5.0	2.0	3.93
2.0	5.0	2.0	4.32
4.0	5.0	2.0	6.09
5.0	5.0	2.0	6.93
2.0	1.0	2.0	12.20
2.0	2.0	2.0	7.68
2.0	5.0	2.0	4.32
2.0	10.0	2.0	2.63
2.0	20.0	2.0	1.71
2.0	5.0	0.5	4.38
2.0	5.0	1.0	4.47
2.0	5.0	2.0	4.32
2.0	5.0	4.0	4.45

(ii) The kinetics of first order in [CAT], zero order in [substrate] and fractional order each in $[\text{H}^+]$ and $[\text{Cl}^-]$ observed with Asp can be explained through Scheme 4.

Applying steady state treatment to the intermediate Z, the rate law (16) has been deduced,

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAT}]}{dt} = \frac{K_{10} k_{11} [\text{CAT}]_0 [\text{H}^+][\text{Cl}^-]}{1 + K_{10} [\text{H}^+][\text{Cl}^-]} \quad (16)$$

$$\text{or } k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{K_{10} k_{11} [\text{H}^+][\text{Cl}^-]}{1 + K_{10} [\text{H}^+][\text{Cl}^-]} \quad (17)$$

$$\text{or } \frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{K_{10} k_{11} [\text{H}^+][\text{Cl}^-]} + \frac{1}{k_{11}} \quad (18)$$

predicting a linearity between $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ and $1/[\text{H}^+]$ or $1/[\text{Cl}^-]$. The plots of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{H}^+]$ and $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{Cl}^-]$ (Fig. 3) were linear with intercepts on the ordinate in agreement with rate law (18). The constants K_{10} and k_{11} computed from the slope and intercept of the plot $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{H}^+]$ were used to

Fig. 3. (a) Plot of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[H^+]$, $[Asp]=1.0 \times 10^3$ mol dm^{-3} , $[CAT]=1.0 \times 10^3$ mol dm^{-3} , $[Cl^-]=0.1$ mol dm^{-3} . (b) Plot of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[Cl^-]$, $[Asp]=1.0 \times 10^3$ mol dm^{-3} , $[CAT]=1.0 \times 10^3$ mol dm^{-3} , $[HClO_4]=5.0 \times 10^3$ mol dm^{-3} .

predict rate constants for the variation of $[Cl^-]$ (Table 6).

TABLE 6		
$[Cl^-]$ $\times 10^3$ mol dm^{-3}	$k (\times 10^4 s^{-1})$	
	Calcd.	Obs.
0.2	4.43	5.68
0.5	10.4	10.8
1.0	19.0	19.0
2.0	32.2	36.6

A reasonably good agreement between the two provides support to the proposed reaction scheme.

The proposed mechanisms are also supported by the activation parameters. Fairly high positive values of $\Delta G^\ddagger$ and $\Delta H^\ddagger$ indicate that the transition state is highly solvated while almost the same value of $\Delta G^\ddagger$ with both the amino acids, in the absence of Cl^- , shows the operation of similar mechanisms for the reactions. The negative $\Delta S^\ddagger$ indicates the formation of activated complexes with a reduction in degrees of freedom of molecules.

Solvent effect on the rates of reactions has been described in well known monographs¹⁸⁻²². The rate constants for ion-dipolar molecule and dipolar molecule-dipolar molecule reactions in a medium of dielectric constant D are given by equations²³ (19) and (20),

$$\log k_D = \log k_\infty + \frac{Ze\mu}{2.303k_b T r^2 D} \quad (19)$$

$$\log k_D = \log k'_\infty - \frac{2\mu_1\mu_2}{2.303k_b T D r^3} \quad (20)$$

where, k_∞ is rate constant in a medium of infinite dielectric constant, μ is the dipole moments of the respective dipolar molecules, Ze is the charge on the ion, r the radius and T the absolute temperature.

Equation (19) predicts a linearity between $\log k_D$ and $1/D$ with a positive slope if Ze is positive, and negative slope, if Ze is negative. While equation (20) predicts linearity between $\log k_D$ and $1/D$ with a negative slope. The negative dielectric effects observed in the present investigation conforms to the dipolar molecule-dipolar molecule interactions, in the absence of chloride ion, with both the amino acids, and to negative ion-dipolar molecule interactions with glycine in the presence of chloride ion. The proposed mechanisms are in accord with these Amis concepts.

The observed non-influence of the variation in solvent composition on the rate, in the presence of chloride ion with aspartic acid, can not be explained by the Amis concept. Applying Born equation, Laidler and Eyring have derived equation¹⁹ (21),

$$\log k_D = \log k_\infty + \frac{Z^2 e^2}{2Dk_b T} \left(\frac{1}{r} - \frac{1}{r_\ddagger} \right) \quad (21)$$

where r' and $r_\ddagger$ refers to the radius of the reactant species and activated complex, respectively. It is seen that the rate should be independent of dielectric constant of the medium when $r_\ddagger = r$. The observed trend in the oxidation of aspartic acids in the presence of chloride ion, conforms to the latter concept.

Comparison of rate data for the oxidation of glycine and aspartic acid reveals that the rate constants are almost the same with both the amino acids, in the absence of chloride ions. In the presence of chloride ion, rate constants with aspartic acid are about 5.5 times those with glycine. Further, the rate is independent of [amino acid] with aspartic acid and dependent with glycine, indicating that in the presence of chloride ion, the participation of oxidant is in different forms with the two amino acids. Identical kinetics observed for the oxidation of glycine by CAT in the presence of chloride ion and by HOCl may indicate that in the former case CAT gets disproportionated to HOCl which in turn interacts with glycine in the rate determining step, whereas with aspartic acid it is likely that Cl_2 formed from CAT interacts with the substrate in a fast step (Scheme 1). Due to the dependence of rate on $[Gly]$, the rate is inverse fractional order in $[H^+]$, whereas with aspartic acid the rate is fractional order in $[H^+]$. The difference in kinetic data between the two amino acids may be due to the presence of additional CH_2COOH group in aspartic acid, the polar substituent constants being, +0.49 and 1.05 for H and CH_2COOH , respectively²³.

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